

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 36 (2021) 1-8

EISSN 2543-5426

New distributional report of *Borboropactus bituberculatus* Simon 1884 from Nicobar Islands, India

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ABSTRACT

A female of *Borboropactus bituberculatus* Simon, 1884 has been reported from Andaman and Nicobar Islands, India for the first time. Diagnostic characters are provided for the species, as well as new photographs or illustrations of the genital organs of the species.

Keywords: Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Taxonomy, Crab spider, Thomisidae, *Borboropactus bituberculatus*, India

1. INTRODUCTION

Thomisids, commonly known as the Crab spiders are one of the largest spider families in the world comprising of 2153 species nested within 169 genera ^[1]. Rajoria *et al.* (2012) ^[2] reported 40 genera and 176 species of this family from India in their checklist. There have been more additions to this list in recent years. These spiders are ambush predators, they sit and camouflage themselves to the surroundings and wait for their prey (ants, bumblebees, and butterflies, wasps) to approach before paralyzing them. During the recent survey in pristine group of Andaman and Nicobar Islands, we came across these spiders quite frequently in the day time. As they can be very easily misidentified in the field as a sepal of flower, bird excreta on a leaf or stipule of a leaf it was difficult to identify them in their natural environment.

The genus was first erected by Simon in 1884 based on description of female specimens establishing *B. squalidus* (Simon 1884) as the type species from West Africa. Afterward, O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1884 and Simon in 1895 reassigned this species into *Regillus*. Later, in reference to homonymy of the name it was transferred to *Borboropactus*.

The collection of these spiders has to be more conceptualized (other than pitfall traps and bush beating) as to retain more information on their natural history. These characters deliver major contribution in understanding their behavior anomalies and morphological phylogenies.

Here we have provided a detailed taxonomic description for *Borboropactus bituberculatus* Simon 1884 which is the second report of an Indian species belonging to this genus after *Borboropactus elephantus* (Tikader 1966) [3].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Area

Little Nicobar is one of the southern islands of the Nicobar Archipelago of Andaman and Nicobar Islands (Figs 1 and 2) inhabited by the indigenous tribes. The island has a total area of 140 km², extending 7° 12 to 7° 33 in north and 93° 31 to 93° 50 in the east. The island flourishes healthy vegetation though it is difficult to survey due to the transportation from Great Nicobar and its hilly terrain. The locals mostly grow coconut in these lands as the soil doesn't support other farming practices, thus coconut plantation being major income source of livelihood for these locals.

Collection, Preservation and Identification

The spider was collected through sweeping of understory vegetation using an aerial insect net. Specimens were preserved in 80% EtOH; for examining the characters the specimen was kept in 95% EtOH so that the color of the specimen remains intact (followed by Framenau 2011) [5].

The epigynum was dissected later immersed in 2-3 drops of 2% lactic acid and then transferred and stored in 85% EtOH. All the necessary details were measured and photographed using LEICA M 205 A attached with LEICA DFC 500 digital camera. The image stacking was performed using the Montage Multi focus module within LAS software (v.3.8.5). For the dissections of epigynum, stretching of legs and chelicerae CZM6 stereomicroscope was used. Legs (femur, patella + tibia, metatarsus, tarsus), eyes and body length were measured following Tang and Li (2010) [6]. The materials are deposited at the Andaman and Nicobar Regional Centre, Zoological Survey of India, Port Blair. The species distribution map was prepared in ESRI Arc GIS for Desktop ver. 10.4.1.

All the measurements in this paper are in millimeters. Abbreviations used:; AER = anterior eye row; ALE = anterior lateral eyes; AME = anterior median eyes; ANI: Andaman and Nicobar Islands; CO = copulatory opening; CD = copulatory ducts; E = embolus; ER = epigynal ridge; ET = epigynal tooth; H = hood; PER = posterior eye row; PLE = posterior lateral eyes; PME = posterior median eyes; S = spermatheca; TBL: Total Body Length; ZSI-ANRC: Andaman and Nicobar Regional Centre, Zoological Survey of India, Port Blair, Andaman and Nicobar Islands.

Figure 1. Map showing the survey localities

Figure 2. Showing glimpses of the habitat, a) Little Nicobar Island, b) vegetation, c) Tsunami effected areas.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Taxonomic Account

Family: Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

Genus: *Borboropactus* Simon, 1884

Spec.: *Borboropactus bituberculatus* Simon, 1884

Diagnosis

Carapace flattened; ALE tapetum horizontal in position and sinuous ; tarsal gland; lateral comb in I tarsal claws; distinctly modified epigynal teeth on lateral lobes; sclerotized folds between connecting ducts; opisthosoma covered with detritus and fungal exoskeleton (after preservation).

Borboropactus bituberculatus Simon, 1884

Fig. 3 (a-f)

Borboropactus bituberculatus Simon, 1884^[7]

Regillus divergens Hogg, 1914a: 57 (Df)^[8]

Borboropactus divergens Chrysanthus, 1964: 89, f. 12-14 (f)^[9]

Borboropactus hainanus Song, 1993: 89, f. 1a-c (Dm)^[10]

Borboropactus bituberculatus Benjamin, 2011: 11, f. 5A, 20A-B, D (f, Sm)^[4]

*For a detailed list of synonymy refer to World Spider Catalogue.

Material examined for *B. tuberculatus*. 1 female; 14.viii.2018; Makachua, Little Nicobar, ANI; Lat: 07°24.480'N Long: 93°42.471'E; alt: 302m; ZSI/ANRC-9424

Diagnosis

The female of *B. tuberculatus* can be easily differentiated from the Indian congener *B. elephantus* (Tikader 1966) by the presence of broad and intricately curved copulatory duct and a large epigynal hood.

Description. Female

Total Body length: 15.86. The carapace is 7.95 long 7.04 wide; abdomen 7.913 long, 6.98 wide.

Carapace: Lateral view of the specimen displays flattened carapace and opisthosoma. The coloration of the prosoma is reddish-brown with light buff-colored hairs all over the length. Clypeus region is rectangular in appearance with PLE on lateral tubercles. Sizes for the Eyes and inter distance AME 0.22; ALE 0.23; PME 0.21; PLE 0.24; AME–AME 0.49; AME–ALE 0.43; PME–PME 0.48; PME–PLE 0.58. Mouthparts brown in color; chelicerae having four pro-marginal and five retro marginal sets of teeth with a remnant tooth visible only in left chelicerae in the current specimen, including eight tiny teeth. Maxillae length 1.78; width 0.79. Labium

length 1.71; width 0.72. Sternum length 3.53; elongated and light brown. Legs brown to dark brown. Leg 1 with a dark band on patella I. Dark coloration continuing from halfway of the tibiae to distal end of Metatarsus. Spines on first pair of leg: 2 short spines at the ventral side and 1 at the dorsal side of femur I, all the spines are located at the distended part present medially; 5 pro and 4 retrolateral dense spines on Tibiae I; 3 pro and 3 retrolateral spines metatarsi I. Leg measurements: I: Total 27.86 (8.36, 9.55, 3.09, 1.05); II: Total 16.32 (4.22, 5.68, 2.12, 0.90); III: Total 17.46 (4.70, 5.20, 3.09, 1.46); IV: Total 18.55 (4.97, 4.95, 3.16, 1.5). I>IV>III>II.

Abdomen: Dorsal side having a black patch with darker spots on a pale brownish yellow colored background. Dark-colored blisters all over the dorsal side. Ventral side light brown with a darker patch along the mid-region extending up to the base of the spinnerets. The lower side also corrugated with white and black warts mounted on them.

Epigynum: Large hood with an enlarged median septum. Spermatheca narrower than the copulatory duct and CD broadened at the distal end. Epigynal teeth short and stout in appearance. A thin layer of chitin covering around the posterior spermatheca.

Distribution:

Type Locality: Moluccas Island, Indonesia

India: Makachua Little Nicobar, Andaman and Nicobar Islands

Elsewhere: China ^[10], New Guinea (Syntype Locality) ^[4, 9]

Remarks: This is the first record of the genus from these Islands, though only described from a single specimen it certainly contributes to the zoogeographical distribution of the species worldwide. Despite the range of forest types where the specimen was found, and the high degree of speciation that is often associated with non-flying invertebrates in Tropical evergreen forests, the male or any other sub-adult specimen couldn't be found; and the studies were forced to belong to a single female. This species is a new record to Indian spider faunal list, thus addition of a second species to the lesser studied genus *Borboropactus* Simon, 1884. Further phenotypical and molecular studies are quite in the need to get a better perception if these two species are well dispersed across these landmasses, or whether there is one clumped distribution for each species in mainland India as well as in Andaman and Nicobar group of Islands that shows little variation between countries separated by several thousand kilometres of ocean.

4. CONCLUSION

The genus is represented by 16 species worldwide having a very scattered distribution in the old world ^[1]. The taxonomic identification for this particular genus has been a difficult task for the taxonomists as most species are described based either on single females or males. The report of *B. bituberculatus* Simon, 1884 from Andaman and Nicobar Islands provides a more scrutinized distributional pattern along with the previously known range extension.

Figure 3. Habitus of female *Borboropactus bituberculatus* Simon, 1884, a) Dorsal, b) ventral view, c) arrangement of eyes in the clypeus, d) I pair of legs; spine arrangement, e) epigyne external view, f) duct system

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Dr. Kailash Chandra, Director, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata for providing immense support for this study. The first author would like to thank her colleague Mr. G. Gokulakrishnan for collecting the specimens. We highly appreciate the support provided by the Principal Chief Conservator of Forests (Wildlife) & Chief Wildlife Warden, Department of Environment and Forests, Andaman and Nicobar Administration for logistic support.

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